

1 **An enamel program activated during spinal cord regeneration in the amphibian CNS for**
2 **mineralization during repair.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the spinal cord following traumatic resection in a vertebrate model of
8 regeneration in the CNS. We describe here activation of a discrete set of gene products functioning in
9 biosynthesis of enamel (e.g., Dmp1, Enam) indicating the enamel program is engaged during regenerative
10 repair of the spinal cord found in nature.

11 Citations

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17 of the tooth gene enamelin (ENAM) mirrors the loss of enamel in the fossil record of placental mammals.
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